

FORMATION OF COMMUNICATION IN MODERN PSYCHOLOGY

Ibrohimjon Mahmudjonov Ismoiljon ugli
Andijan State University, Faculty of Social Economics
Pedagogy and psychology 3rd Stage Student
Mahmudjonovibrohimjon727@gmail.com
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7980269>

ABSTRACT The article reveals the main aspects of the influence of the scientific pedagogical environment on the worldview of students in modern education, as well as the fact that the human worldview develops as a result of the consistent development of the system of scientific knowledge and general methods of knowing reality. It is shown that the rules of worldview determine the life position of a person, the formation of a scientific worldview in a student is achieved not by the influence of the teacher and the student, but by the interaction of society and the student, because the formation of ideas and beliefs of a person is influenced by his environment, that is, society is affected. Worldview helps a person to know the world, its formation trends, the possibilities of the individual and the meaning of his activity. This greatly facilitates a person's understanding of basic human, national, socially oriented values.

Key words: modern education, outlook, pedagogy, psychology, environment, students, system.

Introduction: a pedagogical system refers to a complex, multi-stage, dynamic, information system, with various links and laws. In addition to systematic laws, it has special and specific laws that change the parameters of the order. The elementary structural unit of the educational process is the "moment of formation" of the student's personality. The purpose of the educational system is to create conditions for self-improvement even in conditions of chaos, the formation of a harmonious personality capable of self-complication. We have identified the following subsystems that influence the scientific pedagogical environment in modern education on the worldview of Students: "Teacher - Student", "Teacher - Student Team", "teachers - students" and others. A complex pedagogical system has the following characteristics: it consists of social, interacting objects; works only in the process of exchanging activities (learning, communicating, analyzing less personal problems); must have resources to ensure its functioning.

In addition, the internal structure should reflect the hierarchy of levels, as well as the relationship of the system with the socio-cultural environment. The system must develop, firstly, by solving internal contradictions, and secondly, by correctly "responding" to the "searches" of the environment. The system must be managed through a management subsystem with mandatory feedback (Analysis-Planning-Organization-control-correction) using only qualitative data to prevent entropy or control the level (e.g. in the form of aggression). Uncertainty, uncertainty of results, is a characteristic of the pedagogical system even when one factor changes. The results of the study of the pedagogical process are obtained in an average form. Conclusions drawn on the basis of average results are probabilistic, generalized, statistical in nature. Success in the pedagogical system, unlike the

results of the Exact Sciences, is not repeated twice. In addition, the contextual environment in which the formation of the student's worldview takes place has a great influence. The personality of the teacher, the disciple, is also constantly changing. The pedagogical process has very important characteristics of imbalance (the exact dependence of the features of the process on time and space is determined), nonlinearity (the uncertain dependence of pedagogical features on other factors is determined), openness (exchange of balance), information between subsystems and the environment. The pedagogical system is characterized by the complexity of the flow of pedagogical processes with the most likely result of any pedagogical activity. At the same time, the management subsystem always forms goals, tasks, that is, predicts final pedagogical results (development of knowledge, upbringing, etc.), defines the lines of the possible development trajectory of the educational process (taking into account the influence of the scientific pedagogical environment on the students' worldview), as well as randomness, several scenarios for the development of events are assumed.

Purposefulness, unlimited improvement of the dynamic pedagogical system is limited only by the life cycle of a particular person. The educational process itself is endless. The pedagogical process is aimed at the formation, correction of the worldview of the younger generation. The ideological relations of modern Uzbek society differ significantly from the relations of society in 1960-1970, 1986-2001. The hierarchy of values has changed, the concepts of confusion, norm and pathology have been replaced in interpersonal, including family relationships, etc. It should be remembered that the influence of the family on the worldview of representatives of the younger generation is Kakkad, as well as the presence of conscious and unconscious behavioral characteristics in the family. In addition, the influence of the media, the virtual world is growing in the formation of the student's worldview.

Conclusion: at the moment, the student and even the teacher themselves cannot always find a logical connection in the flow of basic information that contradicts each other. And it's not just about informed critical thinking. In our opinion, it is necessary to study the emerging complex problems of the surrounding world from a single point of view, from the point of view of a general methodology. In addition, the study of a particular object or phenomenon in various courses, disciplines should be reduced to the identification of generalized nature characteristics (subjects of the humanitarian cycle, typical characteristics of the period, general characteristics of mentality or national character, hierarchy). Human values, etc. can be taken as a basis).

At the same time, it is important to train in multidimensional, multidimensional vision of the phenomenon or objects under study. In connection with this task, the ideological function of education is of great importance, since the worldview is a generalized system of views on the world not with certain actions, but with the manifestation of systemic signs of the crisis of the whole world., a developed society and culture, the emergence of a new world. social requirements for the development of personality are the reason.

References:

1. Thomas A. Psychologie interkulturellen Lehrens bnd Handelns. Kulturvrgleichende Psychologie. Eine Einfuhrung. Gottingen, 2020
2. Leontiev A.A., Rustamova L.M. Psychology of communication. – M.: Academy centre, 2019.

- 3.Ibrohimjon M. et al. PSYCHOLOGICAL CRISES IN PERSONALITY PSYCHOLOGY AND WAYS TO OVERCOME THEM //Galaxy international interdisciplinary research journal. – 2022. – T. 10. – №. 4. – C. 743-746.
- 4.Ibroximjon M., Mukarrama J. HOZIRGI KUN YOSHLARINI IJTIMOYIY MUNOSABATLARGA KIRISHISHIDA CHET TILLARINI O'RGATILISHI VA UNING AHAMIYATI //Involta Scientific Journal. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 5. – C. 178-182.
- 5.Ogli M. I. I. TALIM TIZIMIDA IJTIMOYIY ARALASH YOSHLI GURUHLAR //Science and innovation. – 2022. – T. 1. – C. 266-269.
- 6.Ogli S. Y. X., O'G'Li I. M. I. XXI ASRDA TA'LIMNI RAQAMLASHTIRISH ISTIQBOLLARI //Science and innovation. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. Special Issue 2. – C. 814-816.
- 7.Ismoiljon ogli M. I. YOSHLARNI IJTIMOYIY MUNOSABATLARGA SHAXS SIFATIDA SHAKLLANISHIDA IJTIMOYIY TARMOQLARNING TASIRI //BARQARORLIK VA YETAKCHI TADQIQOTLAR ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI. – 2022. – C. 510-512.
- 8.Ismoiljon ogli M. I. BOLALARNING PSIXOLOGIK XOLATLARINI SOG'LOM RUHIY MUHITDA TARBIYASH USULLAR //BARQARORLIK VA YETAKCHI TADQIQOTLAR ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI. – 2022. – C. 506-509.
- 9.Ismoiljon ogli M. I. et al. SHAXS RIVOJLANISHINI MAMLAKATIMIZ PSIXOLOGLARI TOMONIDAN O'RGANILISHI //PEDAGOGS jurnali. – 2022. – T. 10. – №. 4. – C. 140-143.
- 10.Ismoiljon ogli M. I. et al. DEVIANT XULQ-ATVORLI BOLALAR BILAN IJTIMOYIY-PEDAGOGIK AMALIYOT YURITISH //PEDAGOGS jurnali. – 2022. – T. 10. – №. 4. – C. 144-150.
- 11.Ismoiljon ogli M. I. et al. TURLI NAZARIY YONDASHUVLARDA «MEN» KONTSEPTSIYANI O'RGANISH //PEDAGOGS jurnali. – 2022. – T. 10. – №. 4. – C. 151-154

